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ANALYSIS OF NIGERIA'S FREEDOM OF INFORMATION ACT, 2011

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ABSTRACT

Freedom of information law in the world actually predates both the American and French revolutions. In 1766, Sweden passed the freedom of Press Act, which legalised the publication of government documents and provided for public access to them. The aim of this study was to review the provisions of the freedom of information Act 2011, and determine whether the ACT actually provides freedom and access to information in Nigeria. In order to achieve these, a qualitative research approach was used, whereby a thematic qualitative document analysis was used as research method. The study was guided by the Libertarian theory as its theoretical framework. One of the key findings was that; the freedom of information Act contains more sections which deny access to public information than those that give access. The study recommends that; all sections of the Act which deny access to information should be amended, Stakeholders, governments at all levels, media owners and managers should organise workshops and seminars for journalists and the general public to enlighten them on the provisions of the Act and on how to use the Act. The Nigeria union of journalists and other media unions should make it mandatory that all registered journalists must buy a copy of the freedom of information Act.

KEYWORDS: *ACT, Freedom, Information, Journalist and Press.*

INTRODUCTION

The idea of freedom of information in the universal context is never traced to the provision of any country's constitution (Egbon, 2001). However, motivations for

having freedom of information have been as varied as the circumstances of each country that has sought it. According to Blanton, (2002), the momentum towards openness has

arisen from scandals, such as corruption and graft endemic to local government in India, Watergate and secret surveillance in the United States, official 'entertainment' expenses and HIV contamination of blood supply in Japan, food poisoning in Ireland. Blanton is also of the view that environmentalist, Human Right advocates and anti-corruption crusaders have also been in the fore-front in almost every country that has taken the freedom of information road.

Blanton, (2002) further emphasized that the initiative come from the government, although the power tussle within governments usually make a crucial difference, as when a congress seeks to restrain executive power, or a reform-oriented executive tries to limit the permanent bureaucracy, or an ombudsperson exercises particular independence and authority. Whatever the motivations however, a spectre has been haunting bureaucracies around the world, forcing them to ease access to the wealth of data they have stashed away in cabinets and drawers, vaults and safes.

The first freedom of information law in the world actually predates both the American and French revolutions. In 1766, Sweden passed the freedom of Press Act, which legalise the publication of government documents and provided for public access to them. Sweden enjoyed an extended period of parliamentary rule from 1718 to 1772, and the new majority party in 1776 wanted to see the documents that the previous government had kept secret. Today, these rights are built into the Swedish constitution as well as various statutes, and the level of routine openness in Swedish government is probably the highest in the world (Gustaf, 1987).

Two hundred years after Sweden, the United States passed its freedom of information Act, and for very similar reasons. The US FOI Act which has broad coverage and narrow exemptions and powerful court review of government decisions to withhold information, is actually an amended version of the 1966 Act, passed in 1974 by the democratic congress over the veto by the Republican president Gerald Ford (Herbert 1999). American's constitution is one of the clearest embodiments of the concept of freedom. Egbon (2001) expressed this view more vividly, thus: "What made the United States of America to be the most dynamic country and became the foremost super power in the world is the adequate freedom of expression given and exercised."

Today, about 45 countries boast formal laws guaranteeing the right to information. Though complete implementation is a reality in only a few, the response from the public has however been overwhelming such that the total request filed with the US government exceeded 2 million in 2001. In the week immediately after 2 April 2001, when Japan began to implement her freedom of information law, citizens filed more than 4000 requests (Blanton, 2002). Today the freedom of information Act (FOIA) in the US has become a model for reformers and ranks as the most heavily used access law in the world. In 1999, 1,965,919 requests were filed by citizens, corporations, and foreigners (Blanton, 2002).

On the African continent, the conditions that have made access rights both important and hard to implement in the global south generally, are found in their most extreme

forms. This research, therefore, does not consist of a series of stories in which virtue triumphs over oppression. On the contrary, the fragility of post-colonial and post-settler state formations in Africa, the linguistic, cultural and ethnic diversity within particular countries, widespread violent conflict, the absence of adequate economic and social infrastructure, and the near-universal replacement of politics-as policy- making by the politics of patronage under the aegis of the Breton Woods institutions and the *World Trade Organization*, all mean that demand-driven state compliance with the requirements of transparency and freedom of information is rarely seen.

More specifically, as far as freedom of information is concerned, good record-keeping and archival practices – an essential pre-condition for compliance – are often lacking, and bureaucrats themselves are disorganized and poorly trained. In many African countries the post-colonial languages of administration – English, French, Portuguese, and Arabic – may make such documents as are available incomprehensible to the majority of the population.

In Nigeria, the long-awaited freedom of information Bill gained approval by the National Assembly and assented to by President Goodluck Jonathan on 28th May, 2011 and thus became a law. The concern of this research is, how perfect is the 2011 freedom of information Act, and how the journalists have been able to utilize the Act effectively? Though, the Act is to make public records and information more freely available, provides for public access to public

records and information, project public records and information to the extent consistent with the public interest and the protection of personal privacy, it also protects serving public officers from adverse consequences for disclosing certain kinds of official information without authorization, and establishes procedures for the achievement of those purposes and related purposes thereof. The freedom of information Act made it clear on how information records can be obtained, such as rights to access records, application for access to records due to refusal by head of government to public institutions to disclose records. The Act further spelled out ways of getting access to records by courts, materials exempted and documents under security classification.

After the signing into law of the freedom of information bill by President Goodluck Jonathan, many Nigerians were quick to observe that the document comes with so many deficiencies (Ogbuokiri, 2011). However, considering the length of time and the rigours that brought the Act to life, stakeholders were prepared to take the Act like that. However, a professional body; the Public Administration and Management Development Institute (PAMDI) took the lead in dissecting the document and analysing how it can be implemented successfully. PAMDI organised a national conference in Abuja with the theme; “Freedom of Information Act 2011 and the fight against corruption and corporate fraud in governance”, using the FOIA as a point of reference. (Ogbuokiri 2011).

The conference did an overview of the Act, analysed its prospect and challenges as well

as the long-drawn battle towards its realization from 1999 till it was finally signed into law on 2 June, 2011. It observed that the Act contains more exemption sections and clauses than sections that grant access to information. Alerting that, some mischievous public officers can use these sections for unjust and mischievous purposes. For instance, only sections 1 and 3 grant access to information but ten sections (7,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19 and 26) are meant to deny the public access to information (Ogbuokiri,2011:1).

However, the omnibus proviso against denial of information that says; “where the interest of the public would be better served by having such records being made available, this exemption to disclosure shall not apply”, was commended, with the expectation that the judiciary would interpret the proviso liberally for the public good.

This research therefore, studied the provisions of the freedom of information Act by carrying out a document analysis with the aim of reviewing its provisions and determining its use among journalists in Katsina state.

- **Statement of the Problem**

The freedom of the press is an essential ingredient for democracy; the law governing the press in democratic countries are those which only seek to protect the fundamental rights of individuals and ensure the maintenance of peace and order. There is hardly any country in the world where there is no press law, though in most developing countries, the press does not enjoy a high degree of freedom. This is due to the fact that, the ruling elites are always passing

obnoxious laws which seek to protect the selfish interest of those in power (Momoh, 2002). Journalists are passing through difficulty, arrest and denial in the course of discharging their constitutional responsibility. However, press laws are legislations made by government in power at the federal, state and local government levels to control or regulate the activities of the press in their countries.

The Nigerian press after much struggle succeeded in having the Freedom of Information Act, the major problems this paper examined are: bureaucracy by managers who are custodians of public information, implementation of the access freedom granted by the Act, and enlightening the journalists, civil societies and the general public on their rights to request for public formation.

- **Objectives of the Study**

The study seeks to:

- i. Examine the provisions of the Act that give access to public information.
- ii. Evaluate whether the ACT denies access to information.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

- **Press Freedom**

The word press means all the media of mass communication, although the printed media, as the oldest and treated as the exemplar in most discussions. Freedom of the Press according to Bollinger (1991) means the right to publish newspapers, magazines, and other printed materials without governmental restriction and subject only to the laws of libel, obscenity, sedition, etc. It could also mean the right to broadcast through

electronic media, without prior restraints (Campbell, 1994). In summary, it is the right to confidentiality of sources, and a right to access information. Not only is it important to see the press as an integral part of the freedom of expression, but also as part of a system of social control whereby relationships between individuals and social institutions are mediated.

Historically, and considering Freedom of the Press from theoretical framework of view, the press first functioned as the mouth piece or house organs of the few who directed the opinions of the common people. In English common law, the press belonged to the King. This is called the Authoritarian Theory of the press (Anatomy, Onabajo and Osifeso, 2008).

With the demise of the monarchy, the press came to adopt a role in search for truth, a kind of free marketplace for ideas and opinions, devoid of government control. This is the type of press Anaeto et al (2008), called the Libertarian Theory of the Press. In recent years, with media mega-mergers, some say the press has fallen back into the hands of a few. For example, in the United State of America, five giant publishers control the printed media; another five companies produce all movies; and no more than three people control the broadcast media -radio and television (Robert, 2000). Not only do monopolies invite government intrusion, but they make it hard for the press to be a free market place of ideas.

The best that can be accomplished are guarantees of equal time, and a professional sense of obligation to responsibly see that all sides are fairly presented in objective

journalism. McQuail (1987) cited in Ojobor (2002) sees this as part of the social responsibility theory of the press.

Onagoruwa (1985) defined press freedom as the right of the press to “publish without being subjected to intimidation, threat, molestation or blackmail” while Alabi (2003) stated that, press freedom “simply implies that the press should be allowed to publish without prior restraints”. In this situation, press should be free to publish or broadcast what it deems fit to the public without harassment. Okeye (2007) citing Soji Alabi (2003) writes that, ‘press freedom simply means that the press should be allowed access to receive and published information without prior restraints’. This means that, there should be free access to information that concerns the public and making the government accountable to the people. Malemi (2009) opined that “freedom of information and the press means the liberty to say what one wish to say subject to consequences under the law as the case may be; Which laws must be fair, and reasonably justifiable in a constitutional democracy. This, liberty or freedom of expression and the press means two broad things. These are; putting no prior restraints on publication and liability for publication. Ewelukwa (2004) summed it up that, press freedom as part of the international obligation means vital right to receive information and express oneself verbally or in written form without restrictions, thus;

Right to publish and distribute views or opinions without government restriction. It is also the right to print and publish any

material or thing without censorship, it covers the right to hold opinions, receive and impart ideas and information without disturbance or interference from any person.

- **Freedom of Information**

Freedom of information is an essential ingredient of the democratic culture, the higher the degree allowed in any country, the greater the degree of democracy its citizens enjoy. We shall examine the meaning of freedom of information given by various authors.

Momoh (2010) is of the view that, “Freedom of information has to do with access to information. It is more; it is access of the press and public to information held by public bodies”. The argument cannot be denied that all information which government and its institutions hold is public and should only be held in the interest of the public, not as it has been, in the interest of the government and its institutions. This could also be seen as; “rights of a citizen to be informed in writing if a governmental agency holds certain information and requests its disclosure. If refused, he or she can demand to be given the cause of refusal in written form” (Business Dictionary.com). Freedom of information specifically implies access to information held by public authorities is a fundamental element of the right to freedom of expression and vital to the proper functioning of a democracy. It is an act that makes provision for the disclosure of information held by public authorities or by persons providing services for them (Robert,

2000). This means that the act enables one see a wide range of public information because it gives the right to ask any public body for all the information, they have on any subject according to the Media Rights Agenda (2011).

Press freedom is this an ingredient of democratic culture and the higher the degree of press freedom allowed in any country, the better the degree of democracy its citizens enjoy.

The first newspaper in Nigeria was established in 1859 called Iwe Irohin. The paper existed between 1859 to 1867, and subsequently some newspapers began to appear in the late 1880s (Aliagan, 2006). In the early 1900s, the British colonial government started feeling uncomfortable with the press and started enacting laws that were harsh for the operation of the press and finding ways of “checking the excesses” of the press especially towards the colonial administration. Omu (1978) stated that, “the heightened tone of press criticism which marked political opposition from the last days of the nineteenth century to the eve of the First World War could not but irritate the colonial administration”. In view of the situation, the colonial government enacted a law called the newspaper Ordinance of 1903, followed by Seditious offences Ordinances of 1909 (Aliagan, 2006).

However, the Nigerian press began to struggle for press freedom as rightly observed that most of the press laws enacted in Nigeria from colonial times were obnoxious impositions by those in power to protect them from the legitimate searchlight of a dutiful and patriotic press. Incidentally, the struggle for press freedom in Nigeria

was tied to the struggle for political independence. According to Daramola (2003), as far back as 1881, when the colony of Lagos was being administered from Sierra-Leon, the struggle for independence from colonial masters had started to appear on newspaper editorials. The newspaper editorials continued until when Nigeria got her independence on October 1, 1960. As expected, there were provisions for freedom of expression in the independence constitution, but there was no specific provision granting freedom of the press. The struggle to have definite constitutional provisions guaranteeing press freedom was still on. The Nigerian press continued to clamour for the press freedom and freedom of Information Bill in spite of the fact that it did not receive the assent of past administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo until 28 May, 2011 when it was signed into law by the president Goodluck Jonathan administration (Ayuba, Yahaya, Bulama, and Ibrahim, 2011).

- **Enforcement of the freedom of information ACT 2011**

Generally, the FOI Act provides that any applicant who is aggrieved with the public institution's compliance with the Act or handling of his request can approach the court to compel compliance or for judicial review (FOIA, Sect. 1(2)). The question that readily comes to mind here is that where an applicant's request for information is denied or refused (partly or wholly) what happens? The applicant can apply to the court for a review of the denial/refusal within 30 days after refusal/denial (FOIA, section 20). The court may extend the time beyond 30 days or make it lesser than 30 days, while it also has

the discretion to conduct the matter summarily (FOIA, sect. 21). The court is empowered by the Act notwithstanding the provision of any law or regulation to examine any information in the custody of the public institution applicable under the Act, however the court is enjoined to be precautionary in handling such information in its proceedings. It is important to note that the Act in section (29) provides for instances where the court may order disclosure as Follows:

(i) If the court determines that the institution is not authorized to deny the application for information; or(ii) Where the institution is so authorized, but the court nevertheless determines that the institution did not have reasonable ground on which to deny the application;(iii) Where the court makes a finding that the interest of the public in having the record being made available is greater and more vital than the interest being served if the application is denied, in whatever circumstance.

The court could make its order conditional as it deems fit and appropriate in a given circumstance. Procedurally, the public institution must bear the burden of establishing that it has a right to deny the information in an application for judicial review or 44 Section 27 (2) and (3). Akinlawon, (2011); reported that 45 Sections 1(2), 2(6), 7(1), 8, 10, 20, 21 and 25 among others; 46 Section 20; 47 Sections 21; 48 Sections 22 and 23; 49 Section 25

indicates refusal of an application.

In essence, the public institution has the burden or onus of proof under the Act.

Ogbuokiri (2011) in his review of the Nigeria's freedom of information ACT, 2011 observed that the Act contains more exemption sections and clauses than sections that grant access to information. Alerting that, some mischievous public officers can use these sections for unjust and mischievous purposes. For instance, only sections 1 and 3 grant access to information but ten sections (7,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19 and 26) are meant to deny the public access to information.

- **Theoretical Framework**

Among the dominant theoretical perspectives, efforts have been concentrated on situating this research in the perspectives of the Libertarian and Social responsibility theories. The Libertarian theory (free press theory) is succinctly hinged on Milton's idea of free market place of ideas, where truth and falsehood contend; presuming that truth will ultimately triumph if all was guaranteed free expression and access to information. The role of the press in this model is to serve as check on the excesses of the government.

The social responsibility theory accepts the basic principles of Libertarianism, that the press should be free to seek truth. However, it sees the media as powerful and important to modern society.

- **The Libertarian theory**

Libertarian philosophy guaranty freedom of media organizations and journalists as well as the general public in the task of seeking the truth to inform and educate the public, this theory takes the philosophical view that man

is rational and able to discern between truth and falsehood; therefore, can choose between a better and worse alternative having been exposed to a press operating as a 'free market place' of ideas and information (Anaeto, et al., 2008).

Rooted in this theory is the believe held by Thomas Jefferson, the third president of USA, that, if man exercised reason, the majority, as a group would make sound decisions, even if individual citizen might not "where it left to me to decide whether we should have government without newspaper or newspapers without government, I should not hesitate to choose the latter. But I should mean that every man should receive those papers and they are capable of reading them".

The press under the Libertarian theory is free to publish anything, anyhow and anywhere. This however does not mean that there is no law for the press, the laws of sedition, slander and libel still apply to them. Anaeto, et al. (2008) noted that, 'The theory advocates that the press be seen as partner with government in search of truth, rather than a tool in the hand of the government.

This theory helps the people keep an eye on the government, thus making corruption and abuse of office minimal.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a qualitative methodology. Qualitative method emphasizes the value of prose data rather than categories and codes. Adamu (2006) opined that the use of mixed methodologies will promote the conduct of excellent educational research among other

advantages. According to Osuala (2001), qualitative and quantitative methods may appear to be opposites derived from different philosophies, yet both are legitimate tools of research and can supplement each other, providing alternative insight into human behaviour.

The research adopted documentary analysis as technique of data collection. However, there are two types of documentary analysis- Qualitative and quantitative. For the purpose of this research, a qualitative documentary analysis (reading the document and scanning through it and making a qualitative analysis) was used in analysing the freedom of information ACT 2011. Therefore, in generating data for this study, the freedom of information Act, 2011 was reviewed and the data was thematically analysed.

FINDINGS

The data generated from the Freedom of Information Act, 2011 was analysed using the qualitative method of documentary analysis, which warranted scanning through the document (ACT) and made a qualitative analysis.

- **Document Analysis**

A document analysis of the 2011 freedom of information ACT was carried out under the following sub-headings:

- **Right to access information**

The Act in section1(b) indicated that every citizen is entitled to have access to any record under the control of government or public institution (sections 1 and 3, FOIA), provided

he applies for and has no specific interest of the information being applied for. However, one has to analyse the right of access to records as there is no way one applies for information without having personal interest except if the candidate has been sent by his employer. Even as such, the employer provided “*he*” is an employee of that organization in one way or the other has vested interest of his employer as the information applied for may be of the benefit of the employers. Such documents like; Orders made in adjudication of cases, statements and interpretation of policy of an institution, files containing applications for any contract, permit, grants or agreement, etc.

- **Application for access to a Record**

Application for access to record shall be made in writing, the person who made the application as to whether or not access to the record or a part thereof will be given. A total of [fourteen] 14 working days is required to get the information from the date applied (section 5). The fee paid is exclusive. A seven-day extension of time limit may be given according to the Act (section

- **Access to information is refused**

Where access to information is refused by the government or public institution, it is expected that the person seeking the information need to be informed about the refusal and has the right to be reviewed by a court. Any notification of denial of any information for records shall set forth the names of each person responsible for the denial of application (section 8(ii)).

➤ **Access Payment to information/records**

The Act in section 9(i) gave the provision for the payment limited to reasonable standard charges for document search, duplication, review and transcription. Where records are applied for commercial use or not sought for commercial use. The fees schedule shall provide for the recovery of only the direct cost and no fee may be charged by any government or public institution.

➤ **Destruction or falsification of records**

The freedom of information Act section 10 states that, ‘it is a criminal offence for any officer or the Head of any government or public institution who willfully destroys, alter or doctor any record kept in his/her custody before they are released to any person or community applying for it’. The Act in the same section states that; “it shall be a criminal offence punishable on conviction by a competent Court with a minimum of 1-year imprisonment for any officer found guilty of destroying any record kept in his custody”.

➤ **Standard access to records**

Access to records by the applying institution or person shall be released to him in a standard form. Where the person applying for access to information in a particular form and access in that form is refused, but given in another form. In this situation, the person applying for access shall not be requested to pay a charge higher than what has been charged initially.

➤ **Refusal of disclosure of records**

The Head of a government or public institution may refuse to disclose any record that is sought for, provided such will not be injurious to the conduct of international affairs or defences of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. However, the court has the right to override the refusal. Some of the important records that Head of the government or any public institution may refuse disclosure according to section 14 of the Act include information that will;

- a) Interfere with law enforcement and investigation.
- b) Interfere with administrative proceedings of government or public institution.
- c) Preventing a person from fair trial.
- d) Disclosure of a confidential source.
- e) Information that will facilitate the commission of an offence.

The Heads of government or public institution may refuse to disclose any economic interest of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Section 15 of the Act clearly points out that such information not be disclosed are;

- a) Trade secret, financial, commercial or technical information that belongs to the government and has a substantial economic value or likely to have value.
- b) Material/information that is prejudice to competitive position with government.
- c) Materials injurious to the financial interest of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, either Federal, state or local government.

The freedom of information Act allows for the disclosure of personal information about patients, student, residents, other individuals receiving social, medical, educational, vocational, financial, supervisory or custodian care or services directly from Federal agencies or government or public institution. Also, the Head of government or public institution may refuse to disclose any record applied for that contains information pertaining to;

- a) Test questions, scoring keys and other examination data used to administer academic examination or determine the qualifications of an application for license or employment.
- b) Architects and engineers plan for building that may constitute security risk.

Finally, the freedom of information Act spelled out any record in custody of government or public institution is kept by that institution under security classifications or is classified document within the official secret Act does not preclude it from being disclosed pursuant to an application for disclosure thereof under the provisions of the Act but in every case the Head of that government or public institution to which an application for such record is made shall decide whether such record is of a type referred to in sections 14 to 21 of this freedom of information Act.

In pursuant of the understanding of the freedom of information Act 2011, Administrative managers are expected to be reminded by what is classified document. With proper understanding of that, it will give administrative managers the zeal to

perform their administrative responsibility with a good understanding of what classified document is.

➤ **Classified Documents**

Classified documents are documents regarded as top secret, secret, confidential, staff confidential and restricted documents. Such documents must be carefully handled by Administrative Managers under their custody. This is because the contents of such documents/records should not be disclosed to an unauthorized person. Such disclosure will cause embarrassment to the organization or even the nation. Administrative managers who are directly responsible for handling of such documents are to be trained and inducted to take or swear an “Oath of secrecy”.

➤ **Handling and conveyance of classified documents**

I. Confidential letters: classified documents such as “confidential letters” if it is to be delivered by hand, must be sealed in an envelope, stamped with appropriate grading in Red Capital Letter at the Top and Bottom Centre. The envelope must be wax-sealed with office stamp at each envelope ends and must be registered in the dispatch book and delivered to the addressee.

II. Secret letter: A secret letter is also handled as confidential letter. Only that a secret letter is further enclosed in a suitable addressed envelope with reference number and date inserted on the right-hand top centre of the envelope. The letter must be wax-sealed with official stamp and

enclosed in another envelope with the address of the addressee(s) entered in a dispatch book sent to the addressee by hand. Where confidential or secret letters are to be delivered by post, then the posting of confidential or secret letter must pass through the same procedure as by hand. The slight difference is that receipt is obtained and pasted on the dispatch book if any, and entered into the dispatch book or the receipt is pasted on the file or office copy of the letter. If the letter is to be delivered within the country, it is accompanied by a responsible senior administrative officer either by car or by air (plane). The dispatch to another country is done by what is known as "Diplomatic Mail Bag". Administrative managers or officers must ensure no classified document is left on their table while they are out of the office. All classified documents must be kept in a fire proof cabinet under lock and key.

On the issue of destruction of classified documents officially, this is done by shredding, burning or both, and a senior administrative manager or officer must witness the burning exercise to confirm that no documents is left un-burnt.

➤ **The safety of classified documents**

To ensure the safety of classified documents or information, administrative managers must;

- I. Never hand over letters or files or any records that is a classified document to messengers or office clerk unless

they are locked in a security outfit or enclosed in a sealed double envelopes.

- II. Any official that is authorized excluding messengers and other junior officers can transmit classified documents by hand.
- III. Classified documents for addresses outside the same locality should be dispatched through the diplomatic mail bag or by courier.
- IV. To ensure that records are properly kept, there should be no tempering with records. No records manipulation, as record keeping is a must in order to ensure the ultimate security of the records.
- V. Administrative managers must be given adequate training in the registry duties and record keeping.

Records discrepancies need to be harmonised; records must be given to those who apply for it in a prescribed standard form meant for records to be kept. Administrative managers must carefully plan and address the security aspect of deployment of classified document via the email.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Among other findings, below are the major findings of the study:

The documentary analysis reveals that only two sections; sections 1 and 3 provide freedom to access public information;

Section 1 states; "Notwithstanding anything contained in any other Act, law or regulation, the right of any person to access or request information, whether or not contained in any written form, which is in the custody or possession of any public official, agency or

institution howsoever described, is established”.

An application for access to a record or information under this Act shall be made in accordance with Section 1 of this Act (FOIA, section 3{1}).

The Act also reveals that ten sections; 7,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19 and 26 of the freedom of information Act 2011 deny access to public information;

Section 11 of the Act says; “A public institution may deny an application for any information the disclosure of which may be injurious to the conduct of international Affairs and the defence of the Federal Republic of Nigeria”.

In sections 12(1) “A public institution may deny an application for any information which contains-

(a) Records compiled by any public institution for administrative enforcement proceedings and by any law enforcement or correctional agency for law enforcement purposes or for internal matters of a public institution, but only to the extent that disclosure would;

I. Interfere with pending or actual and reasonably contemplated law enforcement proceedings conducted by any law enforcement or correctional agency,

II. Interfere with pending administrative enforcement proceedings conducted by any public institution”. Etc.

The study also found that the Act in section 10 states that; “it shall be a criminal offence punishable on conviction by a competent

Court with a minimum of 1-year imprisonment for any officer found guilty of destroying any record kept in his custody”.

Looking at the above findings, it is apparent that if the Act is not properly amended, the above-mentioned denial sections will go a long way in jeopardizing the essence of the Act which is to make public information accessible to journalists and the general public.

CONCLUSION

The freedom of information Act 2011 in relation to the documentary analysis done, disclosed that the Act provides more denial sections than access sections. This gives an insight that the freedom of information Act 2011 is a right given by the right hand and such rights taken by the left hand.

The findings of this study validate the findings of the work done by Ogbuokiri (2011) where he used the national conference organised by the public administrative and management development institute (PAMDI) in making an overview of the act, analysed its prospects and challenges and concluded that the act contains more denial sections and clauses than sections that grant access to public information, alerting mischievous purposes. He indicated that only section 1 and 3 grant access to public information but sections; 7,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19 and 26 are meant to deny public access to information (p.1).

Given that this study involved a documentary analysis of the ACT, whereas Ogbuokiri's study reported based on an overview and analysis done in a conference held in Abuja. A number of conclusions seem possible. One of course, is that a relationship exists between these two findings.

From the findings of the study, it could be inferred that the freedom of information Act 2011 is a veritable mechanism that can bring openness to the domain of governance and public administration in Nigeria. This can only be achieved if some of the provisions of the act which hinder access to public information are amended, public enlightenment programmes be organised and journalists and media managers of public and private parastatal be trained on information management

- **Recommendations**

After logical analysis of all variables involved in the study, conclusions have been drawn above, inferences are made from the findings and the following are recommendations and suggestions on areas of further study:

1. Stakeholders, governments at all levels, media owners and managers should organise workshops and seminars for journalists and the general public to enlighten them on the provisions of the Act and on how to use the Act.
2. Some sections of the Act like sections 7, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16,17,18,19 and 26 should be amended to enable sections 1(b) and 3 which grant freedom to access public information work effectively without hindrance.
3. Efforts should be made by researchers and students of media studies to improve on this study especially in the areas of implementation of the freedom of information Act 2011.

4. Efforts should be made in involving the general public in the population of subsequent studies.

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